

PREDICTIVE DIMENSIONS AND LEVELS OF SELF-DIRECTED LEARNING AMONG GRADE 7 STUDENTS TOWARD ACADEMIC SUCCESS IN MATHEMATICS

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ABSTRACT

The teaching and learning process is more difficult today than in the past and most educators predict that it will become more challenging in the years to come. As the school locale of this study has embraced the modular distance learning modality on their Learning Continuity Plan because of the new normal education setting due to pandemics, the students are given printed modules to be cultivated in support of their learning. To support this, this study aimed to prove that the dimensions and levels of self-directed learning would have effects on the academic success of students in Mathematics. The researcher used the descriptive and correlational research design and stratified sampling technique with one hundred five (105) Grade 7 students who served as the respondents of the study in the school year 2020-2021. The result showed a significant relationship between the dimensions of self-directed learning and academic success. The great extent of an established SDL contributes to the attainment of a high level of academic success in terms of learning with intention, open-mindedness, and self-management of students. There is also a significant relationship between levels of self-directedness and academic success in a great extent of the levels of self-directedness adds to the attainment of a high level of academic success especially in terms of awareness and interpersonal skills of the students. The study suggests that the use of activities to enhance self-directed learning of students has a significant increase in their abilities which can lead to their academic success and improving their performance in Mathematics perspectives.

Keywords: Academic Success, Dimensions of Self-Directed Learning, Levels of Self-directedness